

HYDROCLEANER : WATER SURFACE WASTE COLLECTION AND SEGREGATION

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Abstract—Water pollution caused by plastics, metals, and other waste materials poses a serious environmental threat, requiring efficient waste management solutions. This paper presents a system designed to navigate through water bodies, collect floating waste using a conveyor belt mechanism, and classify it into plastic, metal, and other categories using image processing techniques. A stepper motor-driven mechanism segregates the waste into designated bins, ensuring efficient disposal. The system integrates IoT technology for remote navigation and real-time monitoring of waste collection. Key hardware components like ESP8266 and Raspberry Pi 4 enable smooth operation. The proposed approach utilizes YOLO-based object detection for accurate waste classification.

Keywords: Water pollution, waste collection, image processing, IoT, object detection, YOLO.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water pollution is a growing environmental issue, with increasing amounts of plastic, metal, and other waste accumulating in aquatic ecosystems. This pollution harms marine biodiversity, disrupts habitats, and poses risks to both human and animal health. Traditional waste collection methods, such as manual retrieval using nets and boats, are labor-intensive, time-consuming, and financially unsustainable for large-scale operations. These methods also face limitations in accessibility, coverage, and the ability to collect smaller particles. Floating barriers, though useful in localized areas, require

frequent maintenance and are ineffective at trapping smaller debris or preventing disruption to marine life. Moreover, existing methods lack remote monitoring capabilities, which limits real-time decision-making and adaptability to changing pollution levels.

To address these challenges, this paper introduces Hydro-Cleaner, a system for water surface waste collection and segregation. The system uses a conveyor belt mechanism to efficiently retrieve waste, image processing technology to classify materials like plastic and metal, and a stepper motor-driven sorting mechanism for precise segregation. IoT-enabled remote monitoring allows real-time tracking of collected waste and bin status, enhancing operational efficiency. This system reduces the need for manual labor, improves waste collection accuracy, and provides a scalable solution for large-scale water cleanup.

HydroCleaner improves waste collection efficiency, facilitates proper disposal, and minimizes human intervention, contributing to cleaner aquatic ecosystems and enhanced environmental sustainability.

II. RELATED WORK

Water pollution has become a pressing environmental issue, prompting researchers to develop innovative technologies for waste detection, collection, and sorting. Various approaches leveraging artificial intelligence, robotics, and automated sorting have been explored to enhance waste management ef-

efficiency. Autonomous waste collection robots have been a significant focus, integrating GPS navigation, computer vision, and robotic mechanisms to detect and remove floating waste from water bodies [1]. Studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of deep learning models such as YOLOv4 and YOLOv4-Tiny in identifying and classifying waste materials, achieving high detection accuracy with minimal processing time [2].

Researchers have also explored mechanical designs to optimize waste collection. The use of conveyor belts, robotic arms, and flap-bucket mechanisms has enabled efficient retrieval and transportation of waste into storage bins [3].

In addition to hardware improvements, software advancements have played a crucial role. The integration of image processing techniques and real-time object recognition enables autonomous robots to navigate and perform waste collection with minimal human intervention [5].

AI-powered sorting systems have also contributed significantly to waste management. Machine learning models trained on annotated datasets have been developed to classify waste into biodegradable and non-biodegradable categories, improving recycling efficiency [6]. Real-time object detection using neural networks has been implemented on embedded systems such as Raspberry Pi, enabling cost-effective and scalable solutions for automated waste sorting [7]. Moreover, the introduction of computer vision in waste management has allowed systems to distinguish between different materials, enhancing the sorting process [8].

Despite these advancements, challenges remain in scaling these technologies for widespread adoption. Many autonomous waste collection systems are still in experimental stages, requiring further optimization for deployment in larger water bodies. Additionally, variations in waste composition and environmental conditions pose obstacles to AI-based classification models [9]. Addressing these challenges requires continued research in multi-sensor integration, machine learning enhancements, and cost-efficient robotic designs [10].

The literature demonstrates significant progress in automating waste detection, collection, and sorting. AI-driven solutions, combined with advanced mechanical systems, offer promising approaches to tackling water pollution. However, further refinements are necessary to improve the efficiency, reliability, and scalability of these technologies for practical applications [11].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The proposed system integrates multiple hardware and software components to enable autonomous waste detection, collection, and segregation in water bodies. The navigation of the boat is remotely controlled via the Blynk IoT app, where an ESP8266 module receives PWM signals and transmits them to the L298D motor driver. This motor driver controls two DC motors that regulate the boat's movement in all four directions: forward, backward, left, and right. The boat is equipped with

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the Hydrocleaner boat system

two webcams—one dedicated to navigation and the other for image processing. The navigation camera assists in manual or semi-autonomous control of the boat, ensuring that it can maneuver effectively while collecting waste.

Once waste is detected on the water surface, the Raspberry Pi 4 processes images captured by the image-processing webcam. The captured images undergo preprocessing, where they are resized to 640x480 pixels, normalized, and converted into tensor format to be processed by the YOLOv8-Nano deep-learning algorithm. YOLOv8-Nano is chosen due to its lightweight architecture, ensuring real-time detection with minimal computational overhead. The model detects objects and classifies the waste into three categories: plastic, metal, and organic waste. Using an anchor-free detection mechanism, YOLOv8-Nano ensures fast and accurate predictions. To refine these predictions, Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) is applied to remove redundant bounding boxes, and only the most confident classification result is selected. This classification is then transmitted to the ESP8266 via Wi-Fi for further processing.

Upon receiving the classification result, the ESP8266 module activates the A4988 stepper motor driver, which controls the NEMA 17 stepper motor responsible for rotating the waste collection bin. The rotation ensures that the bin is correctly positioned to collect the specific type of waste. Reed switch sensors are used to detect the alignment of the bin, and once the bin reaches the correct position, the ESP8266 stops the rotation to prevent unnecessary movement. Simultaneously, if waste is detected near the conveyor belt, the Raspberry Pi triggers the 5V relay module, which activates DC Motor 1. This motor powers the conveyor belt, allowing waste to be transported from the water surface into the collection bin.

The entire system operates using a 12V lead-acid battery, which powers the Raspberry Pi, ESP8266 modules, motor drivers, and relay module. Power distribution is carefully managed to ensure efficient operation without overloading any component. The combined use of IoT-based remote control, AI-powered waste classification, and automated waste segregation mechanisms ensures an efficient and effective system for cleaning water bodies. The proposed methodology significantly enhances waste management in aquatic environments by

automating detection, collection, and sorting processes, reducing manual labor, and promoting environmental sustainability.

B. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SYSTEM

The Hydro Cleaner system is a waste collection and segregation platform that integrates mechanized navigation, conveyor-based waste collection, a stepper motor-controlled bin rotation mechanism. The system operates remotely using ESP8266 (NodeMCU) and is controlled via the Blynk IoT platform. A Raspberry Pi 4 is used for video intake, managing two cameras—one for real-time waste monitoring and the other for image processing.

1) Boat Navigation System: The boat navigation system enables the Hydro Cleaner to move through water, controlled via the ESP8266 (NodeMCU) and Blynk IoT app. The boat is powered by a 12V, 7.2Ah lead-acid battery and moves using three DC motors arranged in a differential drive configuration. Two of the motors are regulated by L298D motor drivers to control speed and direction and the other motor is regulated by the 5V relay module. A camera module is connected to Raspberry Pi 4 for real-time waste monitoring, providing live feedback for navigation assistance. The ESP8266 sends Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signals to regulate motor speed, calculated as:

$$PWM = \frac{V_{desired}}{V_{max}} \times 255$$

where $V_{desired}$ is the required speed and V_{max} is the maximum motor speed.

2) Waste Collection System (Conveyor Belt Mechanism): The waste collection system consists of a DC motor-powered conveyor belt, which scoops floating waste and moves it toward the segregation unit. The conveyor belt is mounted on a stainless steel frame with rollers to ensure smooth and continuous operation.

3) Waste Segregation System (Bin Rotation Mechanism): The waste segregation system aligns the bin compartments based on classification results received from the image processing camera connected to Raspberry Pi 4. A NEMA 17 stepper motor, controlled by an A4988 driver, rotates a cylindrical bin to the correct compartment under the conveyor belt. The required rotation angle is given by:

$$\theta = \frac{N_s \times 360}{N_r}$$

where N_s is the required steps for bin alignment and N_r is the total steps per revolution of the stepper motor. The stepper motor step angle per step is:

$$\theta_s = \frac{360}{N_r}$$

4) IoT-Based Monitoring and Control: The ESP8266 enables remote boat navigation via the Blynk app. The Raspberry Pi 4 processes video input from two cameras—one for real-time waste monitoring and the other for image processing, enhancing system functionality and user control. The integration of these components enables the HydroCleaner robot to efficiently collect and segregate waste, contributing to improved water pollution management.

C. OBJECT DETECTION MODEL

The adoption of object detection models in waste classification has revolutionized modern waste management practices. By leveraging deep learning algorithms, these models provide a scalable and automated solution for identifying and sorting waste materials.

Object detection models consist of several key components that contribute to their accuracy and performance. The backbone of the model acts as a feature extractor, identifying crucial patterns such as edges, textures, and shapes within an image. Once the features are extracted, the detection network processes the image to predict bounding boxes and classify detected objects. Some models, such as Faster R-CNN, use a Region Proposal Network (RPN) to generate potential object locations, while others, like YOLO and SSD, employ a grid-based approach to directly predict bounding boxes and class labels.

Bounding box regression is another essential component of object detection models. It refines the predicted object locations by adjusting the x and y coordinates along with width and height parameters. This ensures that detected objects are precisely localized within the image frame. Following this, a classification head assigns category labels to the detected waste objects based on their visual features. The accuracy of classification depends on the depth of the neural network and the quality of training data used to develop the model.

Post-processing techniques play a vital role in refining the results of object detection. Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) is commonly employed to eliminate duplicate bounding boxes by selecting the most confident detection for each object. This step is crucial in ensuring that each waste object is detected only once within a given frame. The efficiency of an object detection model is determined by its ability to balance speed and accuracy while operating in real-time scenarios.

The image processing pipeline employs OpenCV, TensorFlow, and Keras, utilizing deep learning for object detection. The Intersection over Union (IoU) metric evaluates model accuracy:

$$IoU = \frac{\text{Area of Overlap}}{\text{Area of Union}} \tag{3}$$

Further evaluation metrics include Precision and Recall:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad \text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \tag{4}$$

where TP represents true positives, FP false positives, and FN false negatives. The overall classification performance is assessed using Mean Average Precision (mAP):

$$mAP = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N AP_i}{N} \tag{5}$$

where AP is the Average Precision for each category. The Blynk IoT platform provides remote monitoring and control, ensuring efficient navigation and waste collection.

IV. TESTING

The conveyor belt's movement was tested for smooth transportation of waste from the collection tray to the bin. The stepper motor's precision was evaluated by testing 120-degree and 240-degree rotations for waste segregation. The servo motor's response was checked for 60-degree waste disposal actions.

The webcam-based image sensing system was tested for waste identification using the YOLOv8 model. The accuracy of waste classification (plastic, metal, and other waste) was recorded under different lighting and environmental conditions.

The ESP8266 was tested for real-time data transmission.

Battery performance testing confirmed that the system operated for approximately 7 hours as expected. The motor performance tests showed that the DC motors provided smooth conveyor belt and propulsion operations, and the stepper motor accurately rotated the bin. The image processing system achieved an average classification accuracy of 85-90 %.

The testing phase demonstrated that the system functions efficiently in waste collection and segregation. The hardware components operated as expected, and the YOLO-based classification system provided high accuracy. Further improvements can be made in optimizing image processing algorithms for better performance under varying conditions. This testing report confirms the feasibility and effectiveness of the HydroCleaner robot for waste management in water bodies.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study presents the performance evaluation of the HydroCleaner robot's core components, including the conveyor belt, rotating bin system, motor functionality, image-based waste classification, and IoT-based monitoring. The testing phase confirmed the system's efficiency, achieving an 85-90% waste classification accuracy and a 7-hour operational runtime. The results demonstrate the feasibility of this system as an effective solution for automated aquatic waste management.

A. Image sensing

Figure 2 represents an example of plastic waste collection using a conveyor belt.

Figure 3 represents the classification of detected waste.

B. Analysis of resultant matrices

Figure 4 represents the confusion matrix, which shows the actual vs. predicted classifications, highlighting the model's performance across different classes. The matrix has four categories: metal, others and plastic. Diagonal values show correct classifications (31 metal, 169 others, 127 plastic, 1 background), while off-diagonal values indicate misclassifications. The model performs well for others and plastic but struggles with metal. The background class has few instances, suggesting data imbalance.

Fig. 2. Example depicting collection of waste

Fig. 3. Example depicting Classification of detected waste

Figure 5 represents the Precision confidence curve, which shows how precision varies with different confidence thresholds for the metal, others, and plastic classes. The thick blue line represents the overall precision across all classes, achieving 1.00 at a confidence threshold of 0.778. The others and plastic classes maintain high precision across confidence levels, while metal shows more variability, indicating that higher confidence thresholds improve its precision. This suggests that the model is highly precise at higher confidence levels, but lower confidence thresholds may introduce misclassifications. Figure 6 represents the Recall confidence curve, which shows how recall changes with different confidence thresholds for the metal, others, and plastic classes. The thick blue line represents the overall recall across all classes, reaching 0.98 at a confidence threshold of 0.000. The others and plastic

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix

Fig. 5. Precision-confidence curve

Fig. 6. Recall-confidence curve

Fig. 7. F1-confidence curve

classes maintain high recall across most confidence levels, while metal shows more variability, indicating it is more prone to missing some predictions at higher confidence thresholds. As confidence increases, recall generally decreases, suggesting a trade-off between confidence and capturing all relevant instances.

Figure 7 represents the F1 Curve, illustrates the F1-score across different thresholds, balancing precision and recall to show the model's overall performance. This F1-Confidence Curve graph shows how the F1-score changes with different confidence thresholds for classifying metal, others, and plastic. The thick blue line represents the overall performance across all classes, achieving a peak F1-score of 0.96 at a confidence threshold of 0.436. The curves for others and plastic are more stable and closer to 1, indicating strong classification performance. However, metal shows more variation, suggesting that its classification is less consistent at different confidence levels. The system's performance highlights its potential for real-world deployment in water body waste management. However, challenges such as lighting variations affecting classification

accuracy and power efficiency improvements need to be addressed. Future work will focus on optimizing the CNN model and enhancing the energy management system for extended operational capabilities. The study validates this system as a viable automated solution for sustainable waste collection in aquatic environments.

C. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup for the waste collection and segregation system is designed to efficiently collect, classify, and segregate waste in water bodies. The system is centered around a Raspberry Pi 4, which acts as the main controller, interfacing with webcams, motor drivers, and other peripherals. Two webcams are integrated into the setup: one for navigation of the floating bot on water and another for object detection and waste identification. A NodeMCU serves as a secondary controller, managing tasks such as waste bin monitoring and motor control. The system employs DC geared motors for propelling the bot and operating the conveyor belt, while a NEMA17 stepper motor, controlled by an A4988 driver IC,

Fig. 8. Structure of the boat

rotates the waste collection bin to its respective compartments for segregation.

A conveyor belt system driven by a DC motor collects waste detected by the object detection camera and transfers it to the rotating bin, which is divided into compartments for plastic, metal, and other types of waste. Waste classification is achieved using an AI model running on the Raspberry Pi, which processes images to determine the waste type. An ultrasonic sensor connected to the NodeMCU monitors the bin’s fill level, sending real-time alerts via IoT when the bin reaches maximum capacity. The bot is powered by a 12V DC power supply, stepped down to required voltage levels by a buck converter, ensuring smooth operation of all components. The entire system is monitored and controlled remotely using an IoT platform, providing live updates on navigation, waste collection, and bin status. This setup ensures an effective and automated solution for waste collection and segregation in water bodies.

D. Parameters for boat design

Table 5.1 gives a list showing the parameters that we have found out after the extensive literature surveys and research , where we concluded upon the given parameters for making the boat,This is simply the basic idea, which will need modification after testing.

ITEMS/PARAMETERS	DIMENSIONS/SPECIFICATIONS
Hull material	PVC pipe - 4 inches
Length x Breadth x Height	61.5cm x 36.5cm x 20cm
Load capacity	2 kg
Weight of the boat	8 kg
Max speed of the boat	2 km/hr
Operating speed of the boat	1 km/hr - 2 km/hr
Conveyor speed	less than 1 km/hr
Travel distance	upto 50 m
Battery life	7 hrs

TABLE I

PARAMETERS AND SPECIFICATIONS OF THE HYDROCLEANER ROBOT

VI. CONCLUSION

The system demonstrated efficient waste collection and segregation capabilities, with reliable motor control and accurate classification. The system successfully operated within the expected battery runtime and transmitted real-time data effectively. Addressing minor challenges will further improve its efficiency, making it a viable solution for sustainable aquatic waste management.

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